

METHODS TO IMPROVE THE ORAL AND WRITTEN SPEECH OF PRIMARY CLASS PUPILS IN MOTHER LANGUAGE AND READING LITERACY LESSONS

Nilufar Yakubova

Urgench state Pedagogical institute's teacher

Annotation: This article describes the method of developing students' oral and written speech through the mother tongue and reading literacy classes during primary education.

Key words: primary education, method, pedagogical technology, oral speech, written speech, mother language and reading literacy classes

Innovative, from modern pedagogical technologies using advanced methods and methods using education and quality effectiveness of pupils in education raising, educating young people to be competitive is the main thing facing the educational system is a task. The Republic of Uzbekistan on September 14, 2016 "A State for Youth Law of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on "Actions for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" in February on the strategy" No. PF-4947 of the Cabinet of Ministers dated 6/2017 "State education of general secondary and secondary special, vocational education" in April Resolution No. 187 of April 29, 2019 "Development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030 the line defined in the Decree No. PF-5712 "on approval of the concept". tasks to develop pupils' linguistic and speech competences prepares the ground. "On further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan" Strategy of Actions" defined as "independently thinking, decisive life education of young people who have a perspective, loyal to the Motherland, democratic reforms in the process of deepening and developing civil society, their social "increasing activity" is the task of independent thinking of pupils of junior school age expansion of the potential is active in our developing country under fundamental reforms, it requires being

inquisitive and keeping up with the times. That's why, in giving knowledge, the scholars of the East use independent thinking, expression of ideas, and speech who recorded their scientific views covering important aspects in the process of creation and at the same time, the scientific-theoretical side of speech is found in dictionaries, textbooks and educational and explained in detail in methodological manuals. According to Farobi, how to teach and receive education, how to think when it comes to expression, articulation, how to ask and how to answer, The first of these sciences is about bodies, that is, about substance and accidents naming is the science of language. The second is science and grammar. It is given to bodies how to arrange noun(s) and of substance and accident words of wisdom and speech expressing the location and the results that come from it teaches how to make. The third science is logic. He made certain conclusions how to arrange sentences according to logical figures for derivation teaches. With these inferences we can learn what is unknown and what we judge what is true and what is false."The aim is to express opinions based on the science of logic in the pupils' speech according to Therefore, they use their memory vocabulary through their speech. The concept of speech and its development. Speech is a type of human activity, language tools (word, phrase, sentence) is to use thinking. Speech is communication and the message function, the function of emotional expression and influence of mutual opinion does. A well-developed speech is important for the active activity of a person in society serves as one of the tools. For the pupil, the speech is at school is a tool for successful education. What is speech development? If the pupil and his language work are considered, speech development means comprehensive language development (pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure, connected speech) is understood as active practical acquisition. If the teacher is in sight If it is understood, speaking development means pupils' pronunciation, vocabulary, syntactic structure of the language. and a method that helps them acquire connected speech as an important asset and application of work types is understood.

There must be certain conditions for the development of oral and written speech of primary school pupils. In order to make pupils want to say something, it is necessary to make their speech meaningful, to arm speech with language tools. In order to develop the oral speech of primary school pupils, it is important to teach them the norms of the literary language in the first lessons, for this, on words, phrases and sentences, as well as on connected speech, speech in the process of work. It is necessary to know that it follows the basic principles of cultivation. The work of developing oral speech of primary school pupils should be carried out in the process of learning all subjects, not only in the classes of the mother tongue. Also, work on the development of oral speech should be carried out not only in the course of the lesson, but also in extracurricular activities and individually.

Among the pupils of the first grade, work is regularly carried out on the development of speech during the period of literacy training. In this, serious attention is paid to conducting a conversation based on the pictures, explaining about the sentence, and then moving on to sentence formation exercises. The teacher's guiding questions teach pupils oral speech, written speech, the structure of speech and sentences, pauses between sentences. It is appropriate for the teacher to deal with the pupil individually.

In this case, the teacher should pay more attention to the use of words that are close to the pupils' lives, names of clothes, household appliances, names of vegetables and fruits, names of domestic animals, birds. Instead, it is emphasized that it is possible to achieve good results by giving riddles about certain events. After that, they are taught to divide words into syllables and syllables into sounds. It is necessary for the teacher to make effective use of visual aids. Pupils learn using the scheme and lines that show the structure of speech from sentences, and the sentence from words, syllables, syllable sounds. Great skill is required from the teacher in teaching vowels and consonants, distinguishing between sounds and letters.

In order to develop the oral speech of 1st graders, it is important to teach them the norms of the literary language in the first lessons. It is necessary to know that it follows the basic principles of cleaning. The work of developing oral speech of 1st graders should be carried out not only in mother tongue classes, but in the process of learning all subjects. In addition, work on the development of oral speech should be carried out not only in the course of the lesson, but also in extracurricular activities and individually.

A few for speaking activities, as well as for developing pupils' speech it is necessary to comply with the condition:

1. There must be a requirement for a person's speech to emerge. Read the speech Methodological requirement of development is that the pupil expresses his opinion or something verbally or in writing is to create a situation that creates desire and necessity, 2. Any speech should have content and material. How much is this material? if it is complete, rich, valuable, its description will be so meaningful. 3. A word, a phrase, a sentence, a phrase that the listener understands is understandable only when expressed using Therefore, the speech is successful The third condition of development is arming speech with language tools. There are several aspects of speech acquisition.

These are:

1. Learning the norms of the literary language.
2. Important speech skills necessary for every member of our society, that is, mastering reading and writing skills.
3. Improving pupils' speech culture.

Three directions are clearly distinguished in the development of speech:

- 1) work on words;
- 2) working on phrases and sentences;
- 3) work on connected speech.

It is a linguistic base for working on words, phrases and sentences lexicology (together with phraseology and stylistics), morphology, syntax serves; and connected speech is logical, literary and complex based on the linguistics of syntactic integrity. Consistency in speech development requires four conditions, i.e. consistency, perspective, variety, different types to a common goal s provided by increasing the skill of subjugation. Types of speech. People are from language They use it as a tool to express their opinion. They voiced their opinions they think about it before speaking. This is internal speech. Inner speech It is a "thought" (thought) speech that is not heard or written down. External speech by means of sounds or written in graphic symbols, to others is a directed speech. Internal speech helps to understand and remember the material. According to the method of expression, the speech is oral and written. Oral speech is mostly it is in the form of a dialogue, and the written speech is in the form of a monologue. It is put in the pupils' speech requirements. Compliance with a number of clearly defined requirements for the development of pupils' speech will be done.

1. Let pupils' speech be meaningful.
2. Be logical in speech.
3. Let the speech be clear.
4. Let the speech be rich in language tools.
5. Let the speech be clear.
6. Let the speech be expressive.
7. Let the speech be correct.
8. Let the speech be civilized.

Speech is an important tool in developing pupils' thinking. Speech to express an idea not only a tool, but also a tool for its formation. Thought is psychological of speech acts as a basis, and the condition for its growth is the enrichment of thought. Mental speech can be successfully developed only on the basis of mastering the activity system. Therefore, the development of pupils' speech requires the preparation, improvement of the material, Great importance is attached to selection, placement,

and logical operations related to the topic. Only if thought is verbally formed and expressed using language material grows successfully. A concept is expressed by words or phrases, therefore, the concept becomes an important communication material in the word, which is a language tool. To this concept only if a person knows the word (combination of words) that expresses the concept based on it, will have the opportunity to think in external speech. In speech, thought is formed, and at the same time, thought creates speech. "Speech is thought is closely connected with Without speech, there is no thought, language if there is no material, the idea cannot be expressed." Speech formation of thought is his ensures that it is clear, understandable, pure, consistent, and logical. Language acquisition is of this language to learn phonetics, vocabulary, grammatical structure, improve thought for, prepares conditions for the development of thinking. Knowledge, facts, various information is the material of thought and speech. Speech is the process of thinking serves as an important learning tool. Speech as one of the main dimensions of the pupil's intellectual development is used. The pupil's mastery of material from all subjects and general when thinking about his mental development, the child wrote about this or that topic in his speech in the essay, in the information, in the retelling, in the answer to the questions) what kind of statement is focused on being able to deliver. Thus, speech cannot be separated from thinking, speech develops on the basis of thinking; the thought matures and emerges with the help of speech. On the other hand, the growth of speech helps to form ideas, improves. On the third hand, the growth of speech helps to form thoughts, improves. Other types of training to develop pupils' speech connection with Developing pupils' speech is one of the other educational subjects is inextricably linked with the training sessions. In mother tongue classes, pupils learn about nature and people's lives with the help of language they take; they observe, think, and see, hear, and read they learn to make a correct statement. Mother tongue lessons to enrich the child's vocabulary effectively helps,

teaches how to structure a speech. Reading lesson and related to it The guided tour will teach pupils about natural phenomena, people's life and work provides knowledge about ethics, norms of dealing with other people; in this lesson, there is a wide opportunity for the pupil's speech, its formation and growth. Children are special with special language learning in grammar and spelling classes they learn to hear and say sounds, syllables, words and sentences. They are subject, many words that denote action, sign, as well as sound, letter, syllable, stem, word, word maker, form maker, adverb, phrase, noun, adjective, number, verb, pronoun, conjunction, sentence, part of sentence, primary clause, secondary clause, indicative clause, interrogative sentence, exclamatory sentence; Learned a lot of new terms, such as type, conjugation they get As a result, pupils have the following:

- Effective oral, written and multimedia in various forms and contents understanding, managing and creating based communication;
- Analyzing and evaluating information in various forms and means, be kind to management; looking at different perspectives;
- Ability to work in a team and demonstrate leadership skills; different roles and ability to accept responsibilities; work effectively with others get; be kind to others; like looking at different perspectives formation of life skills is guaranteed. In mother tongue classes, pupils learn about nature and people's lives with the help of language they take; they observe, think, and see, hear, and read they learn to make a correct statement. Mother tongue lessons to enrich the child's vocabulary effectively helps, teaches how to structure a speech. Reading lesson and related to it The guided tour will teach pupils about natural phenomena, people's life and work provides knowledge about ethics, norms of dealing with other people; in this lesson, there is a wide opportunity for the pupil's speech, its formation and growth. Children are special with special language learning in grammar and spelling classes they learn to hear and say sounds, syllables, words and sentences. They are subject, many words that denote action, sign, as well as sound, letter, syllable, stem, word, word maker,

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Forming the speech culture of pupils by developing pupils' oral speech in the course of the lesson is the demand of the times.

Also, working on children's literature will undoubtedly give good results in enriching children's vocabulary, ensuring the fluency, smoothness and impact of their speech. When reading a work with preparatory groups of kindergartens and small children of school age, the teacher and educator need to work on the language of the work in order to convey the content of the work and the main idea in it to the minds of children. Because while learning the language of the work, working with

some words and phrases in it, on the one hand, helps to easily and fully master the content of the work, on the other hand, it enriches the children's vocabulary, educates the skills of understanding language phenomena, and so on. is the basis for phonetically mastering words.

According to the requirements of the four-year program of the primary school, it is required to increase the activity of pupils, increase vocabulary and teach them to think freely, clearly and independently. uses a variety of effective methods to develop his speech. Teaching children to talk about what they have seen, about nature scenes, about the work they did at home, and to tell the story based on pictures, is one of the most effective ways to develop their oral speech.

It is known that children are not able to express their thoughts completely in order, sometimes they leave out the most important parts. In such cases, the teacher helps, by asking pupils questions one after the other, he identifies the important points and organizes the story, and achieves the fluency of its content. With this, the teacher will be able to a certain extent to develop pupils' speech during the lesson.

A well-told story or incident not only helps children express their thoughts and feelings clearly and independently, but also makes a great impression on the children themselves. If the child notices that his stories are liked by others, he will search for the necessary words and phrases in the future and try to tell a full and clear story of what he saw.

As an example, we will give a conversation on the topic "In the garden" in rural schools.

It is known that pupils spend most of their time, especially during the summer holidays, on the banks of rivers and ditches, in cotton fields. Therefore, it is appropriate to start the conversation about summer impressions with the topic "Polyzda".

In the organizational part of the training, with the help of the teacher, the children remember what they did in the police station, who they helped. A collective story

created on this basis will help each pupil to create his own personal story based on the picture. In this picture, there is a wide skirt, and the skirt is blue-blue polish products. Both sides of Paykal are surrounded by fruit trees. Big watermelons in the furrows. In the middle of Paykal, the farmer is collecting ripe watermelons. A bunch of children are cutting watermelons and adding them to the watermelons in the middle of the row.

The uniqueness of pedagogical speech communication is characterized by the fact that the teacher is an educator everywhere and under any conditions. The teacher communicates more with his pupils in the classroom and in the classroom. His speech acquires a scientific and pedagogical content. In such a speech, the rules, terms, conclusions specific to various fields of science are reflected. In such a speech, everything is in its place and in moderation. Explanations given in terms and new words are given in simple syntactic structures that the reader can digest. Rules and theories are explained with practical examples close to the pupil.

The teacher's speech should be as syntactically simple, attractive, and impressive as possible. Any kind of knowledge and education is mainly imparted through the daily environment of the teacher in the classroom and outside the classroom. No matter what form it takes in speech, our values must be strictly respected.

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